
Challenges of Female Teachers in Zilla Parishad Schools of Kolhapur District

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Abstract:

Education is responsible for overall development of human being as well as the any country. The female teachers are plays most important role in primary school because they are better able to understand and meet the needs of children in this age group. Female teachers can provide a sense of security for children in the primary school. The female teachers are said to be more patient with children. Female teachers are said to have a better understanding of child psychology and emotional needs. Female teachers are said to have better caring and nurturing skills. The female teacher is responsible for overall development of child in primary school. That's why the increase the number of female teachers in Zilha Parishadh school. But at the same time female teacher have face different challenges. There is need to overcome the challenges face by the female teacher working in Zilha Parishadh schools. The present study deals with the challenges face by the female teacher in zilha parishadh school of Kolhapur District. For this the data collected with the help of secondary data. The present study is descriptive in nature and has been conducted with an objective to know the challenges faced by the female teacher in Zilha Parishadh School.

Keywords: *Female School Teacher, Challenges.*

Introduction:

In India many years women is work as a labour but they are mostly found in the agriculture sector. Now a days women are entering in to the different private and public sector for job. The different sectors gives the opportunities to the women belongs to rural as well as urban areas. The gender is vast concept which spared over rural as well as urban area also. There is increase the percentage of women worker in India along with that there are different problems face by the women like gender discrimination, gender inequality, sexual harassment and many more so for that purpose gender equality is important at workplace. The Indian constitution gives the equal right to the women in the society. But still women face different problems in workplace and at home and affected on their daily life. Now a days female is top in the education field. The

female teacher face different problem in primary school. There is need to tackle this problem. There is need to improve the facilities in primary education system.

Review of Literature:

Rashid, R., & Maharashi, S. K. (2015). studied titled on “**Problems of Female School Teachers in District Kulgam (J&K)**” The study conclude that, majority of working female teachers in district Kulgam are facing problems like personal, professional, familial. There is unwanted clerical works, paper checking, excess number of students in class, huge syllabus, duty in board exam, inadequate training, excess number of students in one classroom, lack of reference book, less support from headmaster and their colleagues etc. Because of these problem in education system female teachers face the

tension. 2) Amtul Waris, B. C. Viraktamath (2018) conducted study on the titled “**Gender gaps and Women Empowerment in India –Issues and Strategies**”. The researcher said that gender gaps is found in Health, Education and economic sector. In the health sector, most of the women die every year due to pregnancy and pregnancy-related health issues. There are about 60% girls are married before the age of 18 year and about 60% of married girls bear children before they are at 19 years in rural areas. In the Education sector, there is presence of gender disparity in literacy is found more rural than in urban areas. There are about 41% of women and 18% of men at the age of 15-49 won't attend the school. In the Economic sector, one third of women are agricultural worker and she get the 30% lower wages than men. The gender pay gap increase when education level increases.(3)

Challenges Faced by Women Teachers

(2023) Educational blog says, Balance between teaching and their personal life very difficult for female teacher. There is demands of different extracurricular activities, lesson plan and grading is difficult to give time to their family as well as self-care also. some women teachers face the problem of discrimination at workplace. This impact on their job satisfaction.

Objectives:

1. To study the challenges face by female teacher in Zilha Parishadh School.
2. To suggest the measures to tackle the problem face by the female teacher in Zilha Parishadh School.

Research Methodology:

The study is followed by descriptive research design. The problems of female school teachers were identified with the help of the tool like observation and interview of respondents. The study is based on secondary data. The data is collected with help of research articles dissertation internet

resources. In the rural area female teacher play most important role in children education and their overall development.

Result:

In the present study researcher gets the slight review of female teacher performance in the school regarding children education. Some female teacher who are living in the village where they are working in school. Female teacher is more concentrate on their class student. She take extra class for the student. The parents are very happy for their children performance. The researcher is observed that, female teacher is very cooperative than the male teacher. The children feels more comfortable to attend the female teacher class. The researcher observe that, the female teacher face health issues due maintain the take extra class and school work and their personal work at home. The researcher observed that, the female teacher face the various problems like, transport facilities, domestic violence in their home, health issues. The female teacher who are not living in the village where they are working, they report late in school and leave the school early because of lack of public transport system. The female teacher is not updated in technology like PowerPoint presentation. They are willing to learn this thing but they do not get time to learn. Some female teacher face the problem of domestic violence at their home but they do not complain anywhere. The family members allow to some female teacher to take their own decision like spending money but some female teachers family members do not allow spending their own money to anywhere. The study is conducted with the female primary teacher working in Zilha Parishadh schools of Kolhapur District. The major findings of the study is as follows,

1. The female teacher face the challenges related to their health. They are not taking care of their health due to

- overload of work in school and at home.
2. The female teacher should not have time to take her time-to-time breakfast, lunch and dinner. She don't have time to do simple exercise.
 3. The female teacher conduct the extra class in school for their educational development of school children.
 4. The study observed that, female teacher are very happy because all the villagers, staff members are cooperating to the female teacher.
 5. The researcher observed that some of the female teacher's husband and their family members do not support her to their household work and child care. That's why they complete the household work and came to the school.
 6. It is observed that some female members do not have right to spend their own money at their home.
 7. The female teachers face the problem of transfer facility.
 8. The studies observe that the female teacher working in primary school do not update with the technology. They get the training of technology but do not have to spend the time to continue to learn.
 9. It is observed that some time female teacher face the gender discrimination at workplace.

Suggestion:

1. The female teacher should take care of herself and balance their school work and home work with proper management.
2. The transfer facilities is developed in the rural area.
3. The nature of the family members of female teacher should supportive.
4. There is need conduct more hands-on practical training related to technology.
5. Ther is need to maintain the gender balance at School.

Reference:

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